

Russian Organised Crime & Its Connection with the Russian State.

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Abstract

This thesis seeks to shift the research focus from the characteristics and impact of criminal organisations to the societal factors that facilitate their emergence and growth. In Russia, criminal organisations comprised of state officials, businesspeople, and law enforcement members have successfully obtained financial and economic gains. Law enforcement and government officials were tasked with combating organised crime, but they often benefited from these criminal activities and forced illicit businesses to submit to their monitoring. To understand the Russian Mafia's success, one must investigate its background and the conditions that allowed it to thrive in the state.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Over the past decade, globalisation has become prevalent, leading to criminal organisations expanding internationally and crossing state borders. To combat this, national legislation and international legal instruments should be utilised to respond severely to these criminal organisations (White House, 2011). The Russian Mafia, consisting of individuals from various backgrounds, including Russians, Ukrainians, Georgians, and Tatars, is a global criminal organisation known for money laundering, human trafficking, drug trafficking, and arms trafficking. They are in many countries, including the USA, Canada, and Australia (Cheloukhine et al., 2021). Due to the significance and interest in this topic, investigations into the Russian Mafia are extensive. Their operations have a significant impact on people's lives worldwide.

Many recent high-profile crimes have put the Russian Mafia in the spotlight. In particular, the recent breach of the Democratic National Committee's emails has reportedly been connected to the Russian Mafia, although the Russian government has denied involvement (Matthews, 2018; Sakwa, 2021). Broeders (2021) claims that the Russian Mafia is responsible for many cyberattacks on American companies, including the JPMorgan Chase data breach in 2014.

According to Varese (2020), the Russian Mafia relocates by splitting into smaller groups, expanding into new areas, and diversifying its functions. The Russian Mafia is notorious for exporting its criminal practices and strategies wherever it goes. This paved the way for the Mafia to spread into unexplored territories and grow (Varese, 2021). Functional diversification refers to the Mafia's capacity to modify its operations following the specifics of each new environment in which it operates. This enables the Mafia to be more successful overall. In terms of division, this concept describes how the Mafia sometimes divides into more minor, more controllable factions before expanding into new territories. This allows the Mafia to evade discovery and carry on its illicit operations without being discovered (Varese, 2021).

Varese (2020) reports that the Russian Mafia has spread to 26 countries worldwide, showcasing its extensive connections and long-standing history. Mathews (2018) notes that the Russian state initially organised criminal networks in the early 1900s, with former members of the Soviet secret police establishing the group's structure. These individuals possessed expertise in law enforcement, government, and business, making it easy for them to address legal issues.

According to Mathews (2018), this mob crew dealt in narcotics, money laundering, and extortion. As unlawful as these dealings were, the Mafia was incredibly paranoid about being under the thumb of unseen government forces (Gilinskiy & Siegel, 2019). Over time, however, they realised that there were geographic limitations to their dominance. As a result, they had to begin conducting business covertly.

According to Varese et al. (2021), one of the reasons why the Mafia have been so successful over the years is that they have been able to keep their level of violence and intimidation at a high level. In addition to this, the Mafia was very good at keeping secrets and compartmentalising their operations. Finally, members of the Mafia actively participated in corrupt activities without regard for the consequences for others.

Introducing capitalism and privatising state-owned property in Russia opened new business prospects for organised crime in Russia. Organised crime has had a significant impact on Russian culture and government structures. Together with corrupt government officials, it exploits the state's financial resources and administrative and law enforcement systems for its ends. There are two primary types of Russian organised crime, gangster crime and white-collar crime, which are distinguished by their respective personalities and methods of operation (Cheloukhine et al., 2021). The Russian mafia is currently recognised as the most influential criminal organisation worldwide, with an impressive expansion rate. Russian's organised crime influence is pervasive in high society, businesses, state-owned enterprises, and the government.

Because banking, information, and cybercrime do not respect national borders and because there is still room for improvement in terms of skill in combating these forms of crime, transnational organised crime is taking on an increasingly broad range of conditions as a response to the global forces that are altering the world. Consequently, Russian organised crime (ROC) leaders and members have developed strategies that balance illegal and legitimate career paths.

The behaviour and acts of Russian authorities today, compared to those of ROC organisations and leaders, demonstrate a straddling of the criminal and non-criminal realms. Organised crime in Russia is like comparable operations in other parts of the world. Still, it also has several unique characteristics that set it apart from activities carried out in other countries in an equivalent manner (Abramova, 2007).

This study aims to investigate Russian organised crime and its potential relationship with the Russian government. The analysis of organised crime will be comprehensive, covering its definition, origins, and significant global impact. The study will also explore the most effective strategies for combating it. A

secondary research analysis will use academic resources to present relevant findings to achieve this goal. Undertaking secondary research can be highly advantageous in several ways. One significant benefit is the ability to conduct a thorough analysis and interpretation of the information discovered, as pointed out by Bryman (2012).

The selected research project encountered several challenges in obtaining the required information to fulfil its objectives. Exploration is needed to address the chosen issue, which could only be determined through secondary research that has previously been completed; hence, secondary data collection can be less accurate than primary research, which was not a possibility for this project. Furthermore, it gives the researcher access to unique findings, which can be highly useful.

Chapter 2: What is Organised Crime?

Academic and political definitions of organised crime vary widely. The reason is that different forms of organised crime will develop in different environments. Variations in the extent of organisation and societal penetration also lead to debate about what qualifies. However, some generally accepted political and economic causes and characteristics of organised crime exist. A weakness in one facet of society often leads to a corresponding strength in organised crime. Unfortunately, attempts to define organised crime have yielded only mixed results, and no consensus definition has yet surfaced. Despite all the talk about organised crime groups and what they do, defining organised crime still needs to be discovered. This is according to a review of the topic in law enforcement and academic literature (Abadinsky, 2012).

According to the Federal Bureau of Investigation, organised crime is "any group with some formalised structure and whose primary objective is to obtain money through illegal activities." The use of violence, threats of violence, bribery of public officials, or extortion are all methods these groups employ to keep their power and profoundly affect the lives of the people in their communities, regions, or the entire nation" (Abadinsky, 2012, p. 2).

The expansion of organised crime poses a threat not only to security in its conventional sense but also to political order and administrative efficiency. The concept of security must be comprehended in its entirety, as it relates to every aspect of society and the individual and communal levels at which it operates. Moreover, a practical guarantee of safety can only be provided if certain conditions are met, such as good governance, transparency, the absence of corruption, the accountability of organisations, and faith in the government. When organised criminality is present, these essential democratic state support structures are compromised. The effectiveness and severity of organised crime vary from country to country due to unique social relations and favourable conditions (Grant, 2012).

On a global scale, several different conceptions of organised crime have been put forward, primarily because organised crime encompasses such a broad and varied range of offences (Wright, 2011). There have been relatively few attempts to explain organised crime; these attempts have focused on factors other than immoral individuals interested in pursuing personal gain. (Abadinsky, 20). In addition, different types of criminal activity, such as terrorism and corruption, frequently intersect, making it difficult to differentiate between them. (Newburn, 2017; Wright, 2011). The United Nations has been

working since the mid-1970s to develop a universally accepted meaning of organised crime that can be used by police forces everywhere. (Arsovska, 2014). However, there needs to be a unifying behavioural paradigm that can serve as a consistent reference point that complicates efforts to adopt a universal definition (Wright, 2011).

Criminal organisations have varying sizes, engage in various illegal pursuits in multiple places, and employ varying organisational structures, operational tactics, and devices to evade law enforcement and maximise criminal opportunities. (Arsovska, 2014). The broad definition has made identifying and classifying some organised criminal organisations challenging. (Wright, 2011). For the Serious Crime Act 2015, Section 45, an organised crime group (OCG) is defined as "a group who work together to achieve an illegal purpose; a group that pursues criminal activities to achieve their goals as well as that a group is defined as a collection of individuals with at least three members who have decided to work together ((Legislation GOV UK, 2023).

Since it has shifted its emphasis to the legal economy, particularly over the past few years, organised crime is a plague that is infecting our societies and becoming more challenging to identify. This is because it has turned its attention to the legitimate economy. The current and dangerous paradigm that organised crime can be attributed to is that of cohabitation with the political and economic structures of a society; this pattern's realisation has been made possible through deception and corruption mechanisms. However, conventional illegal markets remain where organised crime can thrive, resulting in social and economic harm (Finckenauer et al., 2001).

If the general definition is fulfilled, governments and politicians can also be considered perpetrators of organised crime. Individuals and legal entities, such as corporations, can commit business-related offences. Many serious crimes are committed by using or concealing themselves as legitimate businesses. Ownership, clients, and deals can all be hidden within sufficiently complex structures. Furthermore, complicated systems and legal persons can cover illegal activity and insulate their participants from legal repercussions. Corporations and other legal entities can play a part in a wide variety of international organised crime, including but not limited to human, drug, and arms trafficking, bribery, and money laundering. Consequently, ensuring the liability of legal entities is a crucial part of the fight against transnational organised crime (Finckenauer & Waring, 2001).

Despite its similarities to organised crime, terrorism is a particular type of criminal activity. A terrorist attack always serves some strategic purpose. To achieve political or social goals, terrorist acts are done against civilian populations to instil public fear or coerce governments or international organisations.

Hostage-taking to gain the release of an innocent prisoner is one such example, as are violent acts committed in retaliation for perceived wrongs. While power and control may be secondary motivations, money gain is always at the forefront of organised crime. Although brutality and threats of force are sometimes used, profit is always the driving force behind organised crime (Galeotti, 2018).

Politically, a state is seen as susceptible to organised crime if there are weak or limited national institutions (Curtis et al., 2004). A strong government will have complete and adequate legislation. Their incapacity will likely extend to the police state, leading to poor enforcement of existing laws and a general lack of respect for the rule of law in society (Curtis et al., 2004). Poor governance allows organised crime to grow and compete with national institutions for power in society, using methods of corruption and violence.

One of the most important and least addressed issues is the monopoly of violence. In solid and well-established states, governments are responsible for organising and monopolising violence regulated and delegated to the police and armed forces (Tilly, 1985). Individuals and organised groups can arm themselves and use violence against one another when they are unable to, making order challenging to maintain. An essential characteristic of crime is the ability to use and reputation for violence or threats of violence to facilitate criminal activities or to gain control of an illegal market (Hagan, 2006). The capacity for violence by criminal organisations is made more accessible when the state has little or no control over it.

Corruption is one of the main characteristics of organised crime. Organised crime networks will exploit the weakness in government by corrupting public officials to assure immunity for their operations and to reduce competition in the criminal market (Hagan, 2006). Criminal networks seek to neutralise or nullify government institutions by paying off public officials such as police, prosecutors, and judges. This will allow criminal organisations to avoid investigations, arrests, and convictions and to operate with immunity. Through bribes and kickbacks, they also can gain access to legitimate businesses and further undermine political structures and law enforcement. (Finckenauer, 2005).

The criminal organisations that flourish in a state with weak governance will have a stable leadership structure that can survive long after the departure of essential figures (Hagan, 2006). This resembles an authoritarian, centralised government, which serves to organise those involved and members of society (Hagan, 2006). Well-structured helps criminal organisations compete with the government for local influence, power, and immunity. A failing national economy is a highly influential background factor to organised crime. A state susceptible to organised crime frequently has unfavourable economic

conditions as well. Economic distress includes high levels of poverty or nontransparent financial institutions that are easily corrupted and infiltrated (ibid). These conditions make the corruption of public officials, previously mentioned, an easier task.

While the system of cause and effect is complex, we can distinguish generally accepted characteristics: the use and monopoly of violence and threats, corruption, legal immunity, an organised hierarchical structure, and profits from illegal activities. Another trait generally acknowledged is a lack of ideology, which means that they do not have a political objective and they are not terrorists who are committed to bringing about political change. (Finckenauer, 2005). Some academics include a code of secrecy, rituals or a restricted membership based on ethnicity (Hagan, 2006).

Power and control are often seen as secondary goals by those involved in organised crime compared to the pursuit of money and other tangible benefits. Even when brutality and coercion are used, the purpose of organised crime is always profit. Another critical distinction between these two types of criminal activity is that a single individual can never commit an organised crime. Organised crime is a continuing criminal enterprise that functions mainly to profit from illicit activity. When a society is economically vulnerable, the predominant forms of organised crime provide goods and services that are illegal, regulated, or in short supply, including things the government should provide, such as protection or jobs (Finckenauer, 2005). The government cannot assist; they are more likely to seek help and trust criminal organisations.

Chapter 3: Definition & Origins of Russian Organised Crime

3.1 Introduction

Russian organised crime (ROC) is a network of individuals and groups that engage in criminal activities, such as racketeering, extortion, money laundering, fraud, and smuggling (Finckenauer, 2007). Mark Galeotti (2018) defined Russian organised crime as contrary to traditional and legal social structures, a continuing enterprise in which individuals work together under their hierarchy to acquire power and profit through illegal activities. In terms of its origins, ROC has its roots in the Soviet Union and post-Soviet Russia. It is believed to have originated in the Soviet Union but has now spread to countries worldwide. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, there was a period of economic chaos and social instability (Finckenauer et al., 2010). This allowed criminal organisations to take advantage of the situation and gain power.

These organisations began to gain influence by controlling the illegal activities that arose during the chaos. Many of these organisations comprised former Komitet Gosudarstvennoy Bezopasnosti (KGB) agents who used their experience and contacts to help them become powerful (Galeotti, 2007). With the help of international organisations and networks, ROC spread its influence on other countries, including the United States, Europe, and even as far as Asia. Today, ROC is considered one of the world's most powerful and influential organisations.

Since President Vladimir Putin restored central authority in 2000, the new vory has adapted once more, adopting a lower profile and even working for the state when necessary (Galeotti, 2018). As a result, Russian organised crime has become both a global talking point and a highly debated idea worldwide. The Russian Federation is often called a "mafia state," and some see it as an informal branch of the Kremlin (Galeotti, 2018, p.26).

3.2 The Scope of Russian Organised Crime

The scope of ROC is far-reaching and complex. It is estimated that ROC has infiltrated almost every sector of the global economy, including banking, manufacturing, the arms trade, and even the illegal drug trade (Finckenauer et al., 2010). These criminal organisations are also believed to be involved in money laundering, smuggling, bribery, fraud, and other activities. Moreto & Van Uhm (2021) explain

that the scope of ROC's activities extends beyond just the illegal activities associated with organised crime.

ROC is also believed to be involved in manipulating politics, government, and the media. It is thought that the ROC has infiltrated many government agencies and is using its power to influence decision-making and gain access to resources (Galeotti, 2017). Using its influence and resources, ROC can access markets and resources unavailable to legitimate businesses (Finckenauer et al., 2010). This has allowed ROC to gain a foothold in many industries, including energy, banking, and telecommunications.

3.3 Historical Context of Russian Organised Crime

The historical context of ROC is complex and far-reaching. Russia is, unfortunately, a nation that has provided fertile ground for organised crime. Russian organised crime originates in the country's peculiar four-hundred-year-old bureaucracy, but the seven decades of Soviet hegemony that ended in 1991 were crucial in shaping its present form. This lineage sheds light on the complex relationship between the criminal underworld and the Russian government in the present day. Russia's organised criminal community is deeply embedded in the country's political and economic system. Therefore, one must know about Russia's political and economic structure to understand it correctly (Finckenauer et al., 2001).

Following Stalin's suppression, the Russian criminal world gradually recovered during the Brezhnev government. To its benefit, it exploited the government's efforts to limit consumer choice by infiltrating government institutions and corrupting officials (Finckenauer, 2005). However, when weighed against the events that transpired following the collapse of the communist regime, its influence during that era appears to have been relatively minor.

In terms of its origins, ROC has its roots in the Soviet Union and post-Soviet Russia. It is believed to have originated in the Soviet Union but has since spread to countries worldwide (Lo et al., 2020). After the collapse of the Soviet Union, there was a period of economic chaos and social instability. This allowed criminal organisations to take advantage of the situation and gain power.

The earliest records of organised crime in Russia date back to the 1860s, when criminal gangs known as "thieves-in-law" began to form in prisons (Finckenauer et al., 2010). These gangs, comprised of convicts and ex-convicts, were known for their strict hierarchical structure and brutality. The criminal underworld was further strengthened in the early 20th century when the Soviet government began to

repress dissent and criminalise political activity (Galeotti, 2017). As a result, many individuals were sent to prison, where they formed new criminal networks.

In the post-Soviet era, ROC expanded even further, as the economic and political turmoil of the 1990s provided criminals with numerous opportunities to take advantage of (Galeotti, 2017). Criminal gangs began taking control of specific businesses and industries, extorting money from citizens and companies. They became well-known for using violence, and their activities soon spread worldwide.

In the 1990s and 2000s, ROC assumed even more power by infiltrating legitimate businesses and government organisations (Galeotti, 2017). This enabled them to control Russia's and other countries' economies and political power. As a result, ROC has become one of the most powerful and influential organisations in the world. It continues to be a significant factor in the politics of many countries, and its influence is still felt today.

ROC has become increasingly sophisticated over the years, and its reach has become global (Galeotti, 2017). While much of their activities have shifted to the cyber realm, they remain significant in the drug trade, human trafficking, and cybercrime. In recent years, ROC has been linked to several high-profile scandals, such as the Panama Papers and the US 2016 election interference (Lo et al., 2020). It has also been related to corruption and bribery and used by influential political and business figures to acquire wealth and influence (Rawlinson, 2012). Furthermore, ROC has been involved in activities that have destabilised economies and governments and have been linked to terrorist organisations (Galeotti, 2017). As a result, ROC is a significant threat to international security and stability.

3.4 Structure and Dynamics of Russian Organised Crime

ROC is a complex network of criminals and criminal organisations operating in Russia, Europe, and North America. ROC is highly structured and hierarchical, with a transparent chain of command and a high degree of specialisation among its members. At the top of the ROC hierarchy are the *vory v zakone*, or "thieves in law" (Galeotti, 2017). These are the most powerful and influential members of the criminal underworld, and they typically command large networks of criminals. It is believed that there are about 200 to 500 *vory v zakone* in Russia, although their exact number needs to be clarified (Galeotti, 2017). The *vory* are typically highly respected and feared by other members of the criminal underworld, and they often dictate the terms of primary illegal operations.

Below the “Thief in Law” are the “Bratvas” or brotherhoods, which are groups of criminals who are united by a common purpose and operate within a particular geographic area (Wright, 2005, p.148). These groups are often engaged in activities such as extortion, smuggling, and drug trafficking. They may also engage in bribery, money laundering, and other illegal activities to gain access to resources and contacts. In addition, bratva is often involved in protecting other criminals and settling disputes between criminals. The bratva often uses violence and intimidation tactics to further their goals (Galeotti, 2017). The *bratva* is a significant force in Russian organised crime and has a wide-reaching influence. They are also a substantial part of the criminal underworld, and their activities can significantly impact locally and globally (Galeotti, 2017).

At the bottom of the ROC hierarchy are the *krysha*, or "roofs" (Lewis & Sagnayeva, 2020). These are typically young criminals or recent immigrants recruited by the *vory* to carry out their criminal activities. The *krysha* are usually untrained and lack the experience or connections to become successful criminals. As such, they are often used as expendable muscle for the *vory* and the *bratva* and are often the first to be arrested in any crackdown on organised crime. The Krysha system has been around for centuries and has become increasingly prevalent in Russia over the last few decades (Galeotti, 2017).

ROC is highly fluid, and its structure and dynamics are constantly changing. This is primarily because no overarching organisation is behind the groups (Dugato & Patemoster, 2022). Instead, ROC is a network of disparate groups and individuals, all ultimately connected through corruption and illegal activities. As such, it is difficult to definitively say what the structure and dynamics of ROC will look like in the future.

3.5 Globalisation & the Growth of Russian Organised Crime

Globalisation has played an essential role in growing Russian organised crime. As the global economy has become more interconnected, criminal organisations have been able to expand their reach and influence (Rusanov & Pudovochkin, 2021). The increased ease of communication and transportation has allowed ROC to move more easily between countries, enabling them to access new markets, resources, and opportunities for criminal activity. This has allowed them to amass more incredible wealth and power, making smuggling illegal goods, such as drugs and weapons, easier (Cheloukhine & Haberfeld, 2011).

The demise of the Soviet Union triggered a large wave of migration, with millions of Russians escaping the 1990s' economic misery and political unrest. This enormous departure presented a rare chance for

Russian organised criminal gangs to expand their activities across borders (Galeotti, 2017). According to Palermo (2020), these illicit networks established themselves in nations throughout Europe, Asia, the Americas, and beyond with the assistance of Russian emigration. Furthermore, Chithaluru et al. (2020) explain that the emergence of the Internet and other digital communication enabled Russian organised criminal organisations to spread their activities even further.

During the 1990s, Russia experienced a significant influx of immigrants, which led to a considerable increase in organised crime syndicates within the country (Galeotti, 2017). A notable portion of these emigrants maintain connections to criminal networks in their home country, allowing them to confidently initiate new criminal enterprises abroad. This criminal network was boosted further by the advancement of digital communication technology, which enabled them to coordinate activities across borders (Galeotti, 2017) readily. Furthermore, the former Soviet Union's law enforcement was weakened, allowing criminal networks to operate with relative impunity. As a result, Russian organised criminal gangs have established a foothold in nations such as the United States, Canada, China, and even Australia (Galeotti, 2017; Palermo, 2020)

Globalisation has had a profound impact on the operations of Russian organised crime groups. Expanding international trade and travel has allowed these criminal networks to operate globally, quickly moving money, goods, and people across borders (Galeotti, 2017). In addition, the growth of digital communication has enabled Russian organised crime groups to coordinate their activities with incredible speed and efficiency. The internet has also made it much easier for these criminal networks to launder money and transfer funds to offshore accounts, which are hard to trace and track (Galeotti, 2017).

The rise of global financial markets has also given Russian organised crime organisations access to vast amounts of money, allowing them to extend their operations even further (Galeotti, 2017). These criminal organisations have used their access to finance to engage in legal enterprises and buy real estate, allowing them to launder their unlawful income and expand their activities. Additionally, as global financial markets have grown, Russian organised crime organisations have been able to participate in a variety of financial crimes, including market manipulation, insider trading, and currency fraud. These actions have resulted in significant gains for these criminal networks, which they can use to fuel their operations and spread their reach even further. Lastly, as global financial markets have expanded, Russian organised criminal organisations have acquired weapons and other supplies, extending their power and influence (Galeotti, 2017).

Russian organised crime groups' growing mobility and worldwide reach have significantly influenced the international community. Swanstrom and Wenngren (2017) discuss that the groups have been tied to several high-profile money-laundering instances, including the infamous Magnitsky case, in which a Russian lawyer exposed an extensive network of corruption and fraud involving government officials, organised criminal groups, and banks. That indicates that criminal networks have gotten more sophisticated, utilising their global operations to participate in a wide range of unlawful activities.

In addition, Russian organised crime groups have also become heavily involved in human trafficking, particularly in Eastern Europe. That said, the global presence of Russian organised crime has become a significant concern for international security, as these groups have been linked to terrorist networks and other forms of transnational organised crime. One example is that Russian organised crime has been linked to several terrorist networks, including those affiliated with Al Qaeda and the Islamic State (Galeotti, 2017).

Russian organised crime uses extortion and intimidation tactics to extort money from businesses, individuals, and government officials. For example, in 2015, a powerful Russian organised crime syndicate known as the Solntsevskaya Bratva was accused of using threats and violence to extort money from banks and businesses in Moscow and other parts of Russia (Palermo, 2020). The syndicate was also accused of influencing access to government contracts and other resources. The rise of Russian organised crime has severely affected the rest of the world. This has raised serious concerns among governments and international security organisations about the potential for these criminal networks to become even more powerful and influential (Galeotti, 2005). These criminal organisations can launder money and traffic people because of their worldwide reach and enhanced mobility.

Chapter 4: ROC & Its Relationship with the State

4.1 Introduction

The relationship between ROC and the state is often one of mutual benefit. ROC has been known to provide financial and political support to certain governments in exchange for protection and access to resources. The notion of corruption is at the heart of the relationship between ROC and the state (Rawlinson, 2012). ROC has used bribery, extortion, and other illegal activity to gain influence in government and business circles (Finckenauer et al., 2010). This has enabled them to control Russia's and other countries' economies and political power. In some cases, ROC has even been able to gain control of certain governments, allowing them to determine the policies of those countries.

At the same time, the state has also used ROC to its advantage. In some cases, the government has used ROC to further its interests, either by providing protection for ROC activities or by using ROC for specific actions the government does not want to be associated with (Cheloukhine & Haberfeld, 2011). This has been particularly true in countries with weak legal systems, where ROC has operated with impunity. Better still, the relationship between ROC and the state is complicated because ROC often has ties to influential political figures (Finckenauer et al., 2010). This has enabled them to use their influence to further their interests while also using the state's resources to further their agenda. The result has led to a situation where the ROC has significant power and influence over the state.

Russian organised crime has extensive support from the government. There is more to whether organised crime is big business in Russia and other countries of the Former Soviet Union than meets what is apparent (Grant, 2012). The corporate world is inextricably linked to organised crime. There is an undeniable connection between the Russian government and organised crime because no major Russian company can function without official permission.

The murder of Sergei Magnitsky stands as the most prominent example of official Russian government complicity in a major crime. A lawyer and tax auditor in Moscow, Magnitsky was brought in to investigate a particularly complicated instance of wrongdoing. A group of interior ministry employees in Russia successfully recouped \$230 million in 2007 through a rebate programme. They had illegally gained control of three subsidiaries of Hermitage Capital, an investment management firm. While the rest of the Hermitage workers ran away, Magnitsky stayed in Moscow to uncover the fraud. Magnitsky

was detained and thrown in jail by the officials he accused, where correctional officers beat him. After being denied access to medical care and visits with his family, he passed away while being held in detention in 2009 (Harding, 2020).

Another example of a mafia state is the 2006 murder of Alexander Litvinenko, who met with FSB officers Kovtun and another suspect, Andrei Lugovoi, in a London hotel before being poisoned with radioactive polonium 210 and dying weeks later. Since then, the case has harmed relations between the United Kingdom and Russia. According to Sauer (2020), it was almost certainly approved by Russian President Vladimir Putin. The subsequent investigation into Alexander Litvinenko's death will may well lead to the discovery of additional proof of state protection for criminal agents of the state who carry out significant crimes outside of Russia (Grant, 2012).

4.2 ROC & Its Role in Money Laundering

ROC is a global force linked to various criminal activities, including money laundering (Rusanov & Pudovochkin, 2021). Money laundering is the process of converting illegally obtained money into legitimate funds. It is a complex process that requires sophisticated methods and networks to conceal the origin of the funds. ROC has become increasingly involved in money laundering due to its ability to access vast amounts of illicit funds and its access to global banking networks. Money laundering is often facilitated through complex financial arrangements such as offshore accounts, shell corporations, and other sophisticated economic structures. The complexity of financial crime detection and prevention poses a significant challenge for banks and other financial institutions, potentially compromising the integrity of financial systems (Galeotti, 2017).

ROC has become a significant player in the money laundering market due to its ability to move large sums of money quickly and anonymously (Gilinskiy & Siegel, 2019). ROC groups are well-known for their sophisticated use of shell companies and offshore accounts to disguise the origin of the funds. Additionally, they can use their extensive network of contacts to arrange transactions with international banks, allowing them to move large sums of money with relative ease (Gilinskiy & Siegel, 2019).

The money laundering activities of ROC have become so widespread that they have been linked to various criminal activities, including drug trafficking and human trafficking (Gilinskiy & Siegel, 2019). Additionally, the money laundered by the ROC has been used to finance terrorism and other illicit activities. This has significantly impacted the global economy and made it more difficult for law enforcement to combat money laundering effectively.

4.3 ROC & Its Impact on the Economy

ROC has had a significant impact on the economy of Russia. It has infiltrated many sectors of the economy, including banking, finance, energy, and the media. This has resulted in several adverse effects, such as increased corruption, money laundering, and capital flight (Rawlinson, 2012). Illicit gains of considerable magnitude are generated through these activities, and such proceeds are often channelled into the stock market or employed to legitimise funds via lawful ventures (Galeotti, 2017). The potential impact of the inflow of illegal funds on market prices may provide an unfair advantage to criminal organisations, thereby posing a threat to the overall stability of the economy.

Gilinskiy and Siegel (2019) state that organised crime has taken advantage of Russia's weak government and law enforcement institutions. Consequently, ROC has become deeply entrenched and used its power and influence to control specific segments of the economy. It has controlled sectors to access significant resources, such as capital and technology.

Due to several high leadership positions in industry and the Russian government, Igor Sechin has been considered one of the most powerful men in Russia. He is a very close person to Russian President Vladimir Putin. He occupies various positions, allowing him to keep his reputation as an essential person with many questionable connections and exercise influence within the Putin government (Anin, 2004). The most critical link, which draws the most significant parallels between Igor Sechin, the head of the state-owned oil company Rosneft, organised crime, and government, is President Putin's involvement with the state oil corporation Rosneft and a long chain of oil firms' breakups and financial gains (Jolly, 2022). These centres of influence have enabled covert participation in criminal activity to address the dubious dealings and annoying issues plaguing the state. This practice has also obtained significant financial gain for the state and senior government figures. This is crucial for understanding Putin's rule and how the regime uses organised crime to its advantage (Anin, 2004).

Additionally, Aslund (2019) discusses that organised crime has significantly impacted the banking sector in Russia. It has used its control of financial institutions to launder money and finance its operations. This results in a loss of confidence in the banking sector, making it difficult for legitimate businesses to access capital (Aslund, 2019). Moreover, Aslund (2019) adds that organised crime has significantly impacted Russia's energy sector. It has used its control of energy infrastructure to manipulate prices and increase its profits. Because of this, consumer prices have increased, which has hurt the economy. Finally, organised crime has significantly impacted the media sector in Russia (Aslund, 2019). It has been

able to use its control of the media to spread false information and manipulate public opinion. This has affected the perception of Russia and its economy, resulting in a loss of confidence in the country.

An extensive offshore network is commonly used by oligarchs, business tycoons, and criminals to avoid taxes, transfer money from Russia, and launder illegal funds. The Troika Laundromat cannot be compared to other laundromats recently uncovered, as a reputable financial institution, Troika Dialog, the Russian Investment Bank, established it. Nevertheless, it was found to have engaged in fraudulent activity, specifically the Sheremetyevo Airport fuel fraud, between 2003 and 2008. This scheme artificially inflated aviation fuel prices, causing the Russian government to lose over \$40 million in tax revenue. The companies involved in the fraud transferred more than \$27 million to Troika Laundromat (Novaya Gazeta, 2012).

The state's finances can suffer due to ROC's involvement in corruption. Corruption has been identified as the root cause of the misallocation of resources, the diversion of public funds for personal gain, and decreased public trust in governmental institutions. Corruption can lead to political instability, social unrest, and economic stagnation. Corruption was viewed as a means of regulating the actions of state officials, as well as a factor that favoured advancement. Today, corruption ensures loyalty (Cheloukhine & Habersfeld, 2011). ROC's impact on the economy transcends the borders of Russia due to its widespread international reach. For instance, assaults on firms and governments using ROC might have a substantial global impact due to the high cost of recovering from the losses (Jasper, 2022). The same is true for the ROC's role in arms trafficking, which can fuel regional conflicts and instability and cause economic disruption and humanitarian catastrophes.

4.4 ROC & Its Impact on International Relations

The impact of Russian organised crime on international relations is significant and far-reaching. The common types of Russian organised crime include extortion, money laundering, fraud, human trafficking, drug and arms trafficking, cybercrime, and corruption. Notably, national security, regional economics, and global tranquillity are all vulnerable to the unlawful actions of transnational criminal organisations. In practice, criminal groups can engage in money laundering, fraud, and human trafficking by taking advantage of and corrupting international corporate and financial institutions (Hataley, 2020). These activities can have a significant impact on global markets, as well as the ability of nations to protect their citizens and maintain their sovereignty.

According to Jensen et al. (2019), the instance of the Russian-backed hacking organisation Fancy Bear is an example of how Russian organised crime threatened the security and stability of nations. The United States and the United Kingdom are among the targets of what are thought to be coordinated cyberattacks by this group (Jensen et al., 2019). Fancy Bear has been known to hack into government, financial organisations, and the media to sway public opinion and sow instability. Several experts think the group's involvement in the 2016 hacking of the Democratic National Committee greatly influenced the outcome of the US presidential election (Jensen et al., 2019). The actions of Fancy Bear demonstrate how Russian organised crime might threaten world peace and harmony.

Russian organised crime has a political impact on foreign policy and diplomatic ties with other countries. Examples of this include employing criminal organisation activities to damage the credibility of foreign governments, disrupt regional economies, and sow political and economic discord. Moreover, these actions can be used to bribe foreign authorities, promote illegal immigration, and fund terrorists (Galeotti, 2017). Engvall (2021) gives an excellent example of how, in 2017, it was reported that a Russian criminal organisation had bribed its way into lucrative oil and gas contracts in Kazakhstan. This cost the government millions of dollars and significantly eroded its political legitimacy. Duri (2021) also reports that in 2018, a Russian organised criminal organisation was suspected of paying government officials in Latvia to obtain control of the country's energy business. As a result, people stopped having faith in the government, and the political system became less respected.

At the economic level, organised crime can harm international trade and investment. Criminal organisations can disrupt the economic infrastructure of other nations by engaging in fraud, extortion, and money laundering. Galeotti (2017) clarifies that these activities can make it difficult for countries to attract foreign investments and create an environment of uncertainty and distrust. Since criminal groups may corrupt and manipulate markets and impede the flow of wealth and capital, they can also hinder a nation's potential to grow its economy. A good example is from 2014 when Moldova was the target of a major money laundering scandal involving Russian organised crime (Moisé, 2021). According to Moisé, (2021), approximately US\$1 billion was laundered via Moldova's financial system, with most of the money originating from Russia. This had a devastating effect on the Moldovan economy and banking industry, as well as the broader economy. As a result, Moldova has had a difficult time trying to rebuild its economy.

The activities of criminal organisations can lead to increased levels of crime and violence, as well as an environment of fear and mistrust. On a social group, organised crime can harm public safety and the rule of law (Galeotti, 2017; Palermo, 2020). Additionally, organised crime can lead to a decline in public

morality and dilute civil society's values since everyone will know that coercion and instilling fear in people make one have their way (Palermo, 2020).

4.5 The Future of ROC & its Connection with the State

The future of ROC and its connection with the state is still being determined (Leitzel, 2019). On the one hand, the Russian government has taken steps to combat organised crime, such as strengthening law enforcement and implementing new laws and regulations. On the other hand, Gilinskiy and Siegel (2019) explain that the government has also been accused of having a close relationship with organised crime syndicates, which has allowed them to operate with impunity.

The connection between the Russian government and organised criminal groups is expected to change more. On that note, Poppi and Sandberg (2021) insinuate that it is likely that the relationship between the Russian government and organised crime syndicates will continue to be complex and multifaceted. Therefore, the government may continue to take steps to combat organised crime and allow certain criminal activities to flourish to maintain its power and influence. Additionally, Gilinskiy and Siegel (2019) discuss that it is likely that organised crime syndicates will continue to take advantage of Russia's weak law enforcement and judicial systems to further their interests. The conclusion of this development is unpredictable, but it is evident that the future of ROC and its relationship with the state are also uncertain.

Chapter 5: Strategies for Combating Russian Organised Crime

5.1 Introduction

Russian organised crime groups are engaged in various illicit pursuits, such as coercion, deceit, money laundering, narcotics distribution, human trafficking, and targeted assassination (Galeotti, 2018). The groups are reputed for their sophisticated and ruthless tactics, which entail using force and coercion to assert dominance over their territory and eradicate competing factions. Due to this, the Russian government has implemented several measures to address criminal activity, including establishing law enforcement agencies, implementing legislative measures, fostering international cooperation, asset seizure, and efforts to curb corruption (Galeotti, 2006).

To begin with, the Russian government has established law enforcement agencies intending to address criminal organisations. The Federal Security Service (FSB) and the Interior Ministry are among the agencies tasked with managing organised crime (Galeotti, 2017). Agencies have been given additional powers to investigate and prosecute organised crime activities. Nevertheless, these organisations have faced censure for violating human rights and being employed for political objectives. For example, in 2019, the FSB conducted searches at the residences of multiple opposition figures, including journalists and politicians, alleging their involvement in an organised criminal syndicate (Soldatov, 2020). The action was perceived by many as an endeavour to stifle dissenting perspectives instead of a bona fide attempt to address organised criminal activity.

The government has also passed legislation to combat organised crime, such as the Law on Organized Crime, which increases the penalty for crimes committed by organised groups, such as money laundering and drug trafficking (Lopashenko, 2022). Other laws, including the Law on Counteracting the Legalization (Laundering) of Criminally Obtained Incomes, have been introduced to combat types of organised crime (Khazratoli, 2023). However, detractors contend these regulations can be inconsistently applied, frequently ambiguous, and susceptible to interpretation. Concerns have also been raised concerning how these rules are applied selectively, with some groups allegedly receiving preferential treatment while others are relentlessly pursued (Khazratoli, 2023).

To combat organised crime activities that involve transnational criminal activity, the government has additionally worked with foreign law enforcement agencies (Shelley, 2002). For instance, the FBI and

other international law enforcement agencies have collaborated with the Russian government to investigate and prosecute cases involving Russian organised crime groups that operate abroad (Galeotti, 2017). Although fighting transnational organised crime can be effectively accomplished with international cooperation, there have been worries about the politicisation of such collaboration. In contrast to concentrating simply on fighting organised crime, the Russian government has been charged with exploiting its cooperation with foreign law enforcement agencies to serve its geopolitical aims.

In addition, Zagaris et al. (2022) explain that the Russian government has taken control of the enterprises, real estate, and financial assets owned by organised crime organisations to sabotage their activities and economic networks. Additionally, these seizures may operate as a deterrence to other individuals engaged in organised crime activities. The fairness and transparency of confiscating assets in Russia have raised questions, though, particularly in situations where the government has been accused of using the seizures to attack political opponents (Moiseienko, 2022). Additionally, asset seizures have occurred without due legal procedure or payment to affected individuals.

Finally, governmental authorities have implemented strategies to tackle corruption within law enforcement agencies and the government, as corrupt officials may enable the operations of organised criminal factions (Kirin et al., 2020). For example, the government has established anti-corruption bodies such as the Federal Anti-Corruption Bureau and the Presidential Anti-Corruption Council (Kirin et al., 2020). Critics contend that the measures above exhibit a tendency towards selectivity and politicisation, whereby the focus of anti-corruption endeavours is primarily directed towards political adversaries rather than authentic instances of corruption (Shelley, 2002). Furthermore, corruption in various sectors of Russian society poses a significant challenge to effectively mitigating organised crime, necessitating the prioritisation of anti-corruption measures.

Russia's government has likely used various strategies to combat organised crime. The techniques include the formation of specialised law enforcement agencies, the introduction of new legal measures, the establishment of partnerships with foreign law enforcement agencies, the seizure of assets associated with international criminal organisations, and the implementation of anti-corruption legislation (Shelley, 2002; Kirin et al., 2020). Despite the efforts, concerns and obstacles still need to be overcome, such as a lack of transparency, unequal performance, and the links between organised crime and corruption. Russia's organised crime problem requires a long-term, all-encompassing strategy that tackles root causes like corruption.

5.2 International Efforts to Combat Russian Organised Crime

International governments have adopted various methods to tackle Russian organised crime organisations outside Russia. Some of these tactics resemble those employed by the Russian government. The international community uses law enforcement cooperation as a starting point (Galeotti, 2017). To combat illicit financial activities and exceedingly organised crime, the United States and Russia launched a Joint Economic and Financial Partnership (JEF) in 2013. Improving communication and cooperation between US and Russian law enforcement agencies was one of the JEF's main objectives. This goal was met by sharing knowledge, insight, and experience on economic and financial crime investigations. To lessen the financial sector's susceptibility to criminal activities, the partnership also sought to advance the creation of best practices and standards for financial regulation and compliance. Another illustration is the collaboration between the Russian Interior Ministry and the UK's National Crime Agency (NCA), which tries to target Russian organised crime groups operating in the UK (Ryder et al., 2023).

International governments have embraced legislation as a crucial instrument to combat organised crime, especially in transnational criminal operations (Galeotti, 2017). These measures are intended to give law enforcement authorities more resources and tools to investigate and punish organised crime and discourage people from participating in such activities. One illustration of such legislative actions is the Global Magnitsky Act, which the US government passed in 2016 (Hamer, 2020). The statute imposes penalties like asset freezes and travel restrictions on those responsible for corruption and human rights violations. The law bears Sergei Magnitsky's name, a Russian attorney who died in detention after exposing a significant fraud scheme involving Russian government officials. The statute has been used to punish members of Russian organised criminal groups and government representatives responsible for human rights violations in nations like North Korea and Venezuela (Hamer, 2020).

Organised crime has been fought with financial sanctions as well. International governments, like the European Union and the United States, have placed economic sanctions on people and companies suspected of being involved in organised crime, freezing their assets and barring them from conducting business in those nations. The UK's National Crime Agency has also utilised Unexplained Wealth Orders to seize the support of those thought to be connected to organised crime. Some governments have used extradition in addition to these penalties to stop the spread of organised criminal groups. Several high-profile Russian organised crime members who were extradited to the United States are just a few examples of the people whose extradition has been requested by governments so they can stand prosecution for their alleged involvement in organised crime at home. An illustration is prominent

Russian organised crime figure Semion Mogilevich, who was successfully extradited to the US from Hungary in 2010 to face charges there (Galeotti, 2017). In 2012, Gennady Petrov, a prominent member of Russian organised crime, was also extradited from Spain to the UK to face fraud and money laundering charges.

Regarding combating Russian organised crime, certain countries have opted to share intelligence (Naim, 2012). This approach has allowed for better tracking of the actions of Russian criminal organisations, which has hampered their ability to operate and launder money. Galeotti (2017) provides an example of how this phenomenon manifests itself by describing how international law enforcement agencies use Interpol to share intelligence about Russian organised crime groups and their activities. The National Crime Agency (NCA) of the United Kingdom and the Interior Ministry of Russia also cooperate in the exchange of intelligence regarding criminal links and trends to expedite the detention and extradition of members of criminal organisations (Galeotti, 2017).

Governments have deployed various tactics to stymie criminal organisations' operations as part of the worldwide effort to counter Russian organised crime. The abovementioned strategies include law enforcement cooperation, legal action, monetary fines, extradition, and information sharing. While these efforts have yielded some successes, many challenges remain. These include the difficulty of worldwide coordination, the lack of ethics among participants, and the adaptability of criminal organisations. However, international cooperation, information-sharing, and perspectives are vital to combat criminal groups' dangers in Russia (Shelley, 2002). When governments work together in a concerted effort over an extended period, they have the potential to make significant headway in disrupting criminal organisations and preventing the ill impacts those organisations have on both individuals and the larger community.

5.3 Conclusions & Implications

The future of ROC and its connection with the state is still being determined. The government will likely continue to take steps to combat organised crime, but it will also continue to allow certain criminal activities to flourish to maintain its power and influence. Additionally, organised crime syndicates will likely continue to take advantage of Russia's weak law enforcement and judicial systems to further their interests. The implications of these conclusions are clear. It is essential that the government continues to take steps to combat organised crime in Russia and that international organisations continue to target the activities of ROC syndicates. Additionally, the government must strengthen law enforcement, increase public awareness, and target the most influential members of organised crime syndicates.

Ultimately, it is only through a concerted effort on all these fronts that the scourge of ROC can be successfully addressed.

The connection between Russian organised crime (ROC) and the government is complex and diverse. Reports show that some ROC groups collaborate with law enforcement officials and government actors, especially regarding corruption and money laundering. ROC groups have cooperated with the state by offering information to law enforcement agencies, bribing government officials, or using state institutions to launder money. In some instances, ROC groups have significant control over state regions, which can result in them having expert authority over political decisions, manipulating elections, and utilising law enforcement to eliminate competition (Galeotti, 2017).

The Russian Mafia is integrated into society in various ways, with its members including economists, bankers, and government officials. Some government officials operate in a grey area, engaging in activities like those of organised crime groups and utilising criminal networks as part of their business strategy. Over time, Russian organised crime has shifted away from being strictly part of the criminal underworld and has become more intertwined with the state. While organised crime has not overtaken the government, there is a coexistence between the two, with illegal and legal networks continuing to have interconnected relationships within the Russian government.

The impact of the ROC on Russia's economy and international relations has been significant. The group has managed to infiltrate various sectors, including banking, finance, energy, and media. Not only has there been a growing mutual dependence between organised crime and the state in recent years, but there has also been a growing intertwining nature in which Russian officials are the perpetrators of organised crime. This has led to negative consequences, such as higher levels of corruption, money laundering, and capital flight. There is a lack of transparency and responsibility in the decision-making process, and only a tiny percentage of those accused of corruption are found guilty in court. To address this issue, the government has implemented measures such as boosting law enforcement, raising public awareness, and targeting the most influential members of these crime syndicates. Additionally, the government's close ties with these criminal groups have enabled them to operate more efficiently (Anin, 2004).

Many countries and international organisations have tried to combat ROC syndicates, but their efforts have kept ROC activity the same. The measures taken have had the opposite effect, revealing the corrupt nature of law enforcement officials who help ROC conceal their crimes (Sukharensko & Lesneskie). Finally, it should be noted that Russian organised crime has dominated global crime for

many years. The ROC–Russian relationship has a complicated history, including cooperation and conflict. The ROC is a worldwide power due to its connection to various criminal enterprises. It is unknown how the ROC will respond to changes in the world’s criminal landscape or how it will interact with the government. International engagement and cooperation in the fight against organised crime are crucial in the battle against the ROC and other criminal organisations.

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